

THE EFFECT OF PSYCHOLOGY INTERVENTION TRAINING PROGRAMME ON COMPETITIVE ANXIETY, AND THEIR PERFORMANCE OF SHOT-PUT ATHLETES

Dr. Lohote P. K.

Director of Physical Education, Mahatma Phule Mahavidyalaya, Pimpri, Pune - 17

Abstract:

Studies related to effect of Competitive State anxiety and competitive performance has become a major topic of interest to sports psychologist in recent years. The present study is mainly concerned with anxiety in shot put athletes and its relation with their performance who participated in the state level competition. A researcher himself, being an athlete, has experienced such situations and hence was curious to study the effect of competitive state anxiety and performance. The researcher in his own performance at practice sessions and national competitions showed considerable difference. According to researcher anxiety might have been a major factor for such results. After being in contact with many similar athletes and coaches the researcher has found that similar problems are faced even today. Hence the researcher decided on performing a study on shot-put athletes and sees the effect of anxiety on their performances.

The study was a Survey with experimental research one group pretest posttest Experimental research. The male shot-put 19 athletes of the Maharashtra state aged between 16-18 years will be considered as the total population of the study. The sample of the study was selected using convenience sampling method. For data collection the tools used was the Competitive State Anxiety inventory -2 (CSAI-2) by Martens, Vealey, & Burton (1990). The specific tool measures, cognitive, somatic anxiety, & self-confidence. Pearson Correlation method was used for this propose.

The 't' test for paired observation was used to determine whether group improved significantly in performance and optimal anxiety after training. Post test showed significance difference has been found performance and anxiety level due to training module. The result of the research showed shot- put male athletes reported reduce of Cognitive Anxiety and Somatic Anxiety and high level Self Confidence. Furthermore these athletes displayed higher self-confidence with positive effect on their performance. Cognitive anxiety and somatic anxiety are positively correlated.

Key world: *Self- Confidence, Cognitive anxiety, Somatic anxiety, Performance*

Introduction:

Studies related to effect of Competitive State anxiety and competitive performance has become a major topic of interest to sports psychologist in recent years. The present study is mainly concerned with anxiety in shot put athletes and its relation with their performance who participated in the state level competition. A researcher himself, being an athlete, has experienced such situations and hence was curious to study the effect of competitive state anxiety and performance. The researcher in his own performance at practice sessions and national competitions showed considerable difference. According to researcher anxiety might have been a major factor for such results. After being in contact with many similar athletes and coaches the researcher has found that similar problems are faced even today. Hence the researcher decided on performing a study on shot-put athletes and sees the effect of anxiety on their performances.

Methodology : The present study was a Survey with experimental research one group pretest post test

Experimental research..The male shot-put 19 athletes of the Maharashtra state aged between 16-18 years will be considered as the total population of the study. The sample of the study was selected using convenience sampling method.For data collection the tools used was the Competitive State Anxiety inventory -2 (CSAI-2) by Martens, Vealey, & Burton (1990).Paired Sample statistics used for these present study.

Analysis of Data : Paired Sample statistics

Table 1.1

Paired Sample statistics Pre performance and Post Performance of Shot-Put athletes

Test	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pre	12.74	19	1.15	0.26
Post	13.07	19	0.92	0.21

Table 1.1 shows that mean performance of Shot-Put athletes at pre test level was 12.74 meters with Std Deviation 1.15 similarly mean post test level performance of Shot- Put athletes was13.07 meters with S.D. 0.92 meters.

Table 1.2

Paired Sample statistics of Pre and Post Cognitive Anxiety of Shot-Put athletes

Test	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pre	23.84	19	2.77	0.64
Post	21.47	19	2.43	0.56

Table 1.2 shows that mean of Pre and Post Cognitive Anxiety Shot-Put athletes at pre test level was 23.84 meters with Std Deviation 2.77 meters similarly mean post test level performance of Shot-Put athletes was 21.47 meters with S.D. 2.43 meters.

Table 1.3

Paired Sample statistics of Pre and Post Somatic of Shot-Put athletes

Test	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pre	24.68	19	3.09	0.71
Post	21.36	19	3.53	0.81

Table 1.3 shows that Mean of Pre Somatic Anxiety of Shot-Put athletes at pre test level was 24.68 with Std Deviation 3.09, similarly mean post test level Somatic Anxiety of Shot-Put athletes was 21.37 with S.D. 3.53.

Table 1.4

Paired Sample statistics of Pre S and Post Self-confidenceof Shot-Put athletes

Test	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pre	25.16	19	3.67	0.84
Post	26.68	19	3.25	0.74

Table 1.4 shows that mean Pre Self Confidence of Shot-Put athletesat pre test level was 25.16 with Std Deviation 3.67 similarly mean post test level Self confidence of Shot-Put athleteswas 26.68 with S.D. 3.25.

Table 1.5
Paired Samples 't' Test of Pre and Post Performance of Shot-Put athletes

	Mean Difference (Meter)	Std Deviation	T	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
Pre -Post performance	-0.32	0.37	-3.76	18	.01

Table 1.5 shows that the Mean of difference between the pre test and post test Shot-Put athletes performance was -0.32 meters (SD= 0.37). This difference was tested with pair sample t-test and it shows that this performance was statistically significant at 0.01 level of significance ($t = -3.77$, $df = 18$)

Table 1.6
Paired Sample Correlation of Pre and Post Test Performance of Shot-Put athletes

N	Correlation	Sig.
19	0.96	0.00

Table 1.6 show correlation between Pre Test and Post Test Performance of Shot-Put athletes was .96 which was statistically Significant at 0.01 level of significance ($p = 0.00$).

Table 1.7
Paired Samples 't' Test of Pre and Post Cognitive Anxiety of Shot-Put athletes

	Mean Difference (Meter)	Std Deviation	T	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
Pre-Post Cognitive Anxiety	2.37	2.19	4.71	18	0.00

Table 1.7 shows that the Mean difference between the Pre Cognitive Anxiety and Post Cognitive Anxiety of Shot-Put athletes was 2.37 meters (SD= 2.19). This difference was tested with pair sample t-test and it shows that Pre and Post Cognitive Anxiety was statistically significant at 0.01 level of significance ($t = 4.71$, $df = 18$)

Table 1.8
Paired Sample Correlation of Pre and Post Cognitive Anxiety of Shot-Put athletes

N	Correlation	Sig.
19	0.65	0.00

Table 1.8 show correlation between Pre Test and Post test Cognitive Anxiety Shot-Put athletes and was 0.65 which was statistically Significant at 0.01 level of significance ($p = 0.00$).

Table 1.9
Paired Samples 't' Test of Pre and Post Somatic Anxiety of Shot-Put athletes

	Mean Difference (Meter)	Std Deviation	T	Df	Sig.(2-tailed)
Pre- Post Somatic Anxiety	3.31	3.90	3.70	18	0.00

Table 1.9 shows that the Mean difference between the Pre Somatic Anxiety and Post Somatic Anxiety of Shot-Put athletes was 3.31 (SD= 3.90). This difference was tested with pair sample t-test it shows that Pre and Post Cognitive Anxiety was statistically significant at 0.01 level of significance ($t = 3.70$, $df = 18$)

Table 1.10
Paired Sample Correlation of Pre Test and Post Test Somatic Anxiety of Shot-Put

N	Correlation	Sig.
19	0.31	0.19

Table 1.10 show correlation between Pre Test and Post test Somatic Anxiety of Shot- Put athletes was 0.31 which was statistically not Significant at 0.01 level of significance ($p=0.19$).

Table 1.11
Paired Samples 't' Test of Pre and Post Self-confidence of Shot-Put athletes

	Mean Difference (Meter)	Std Deviation	T	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
Pre- Post Self confidence	-1.53	3.32	-1.52	18	0.05

Table 1.11 shows that the Mean difference between the Pre Self Confidence and Post Self Confidence of Shot-Put athletes was -1.53 (SD= 3.32). This difference was tested with pair sample t-test its show that this performance was statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance ($t = -1.52$, $df=18$)

Table 1.12
Paired Sample Correlation of Pre and Post Test Self Confidence of Shot-Put athletes

N	Correlation	Sig.
19	0.54	0.01

Table 1.12 show correlation between Pre Test and Post Test Self-confidence Shot-Put athletes was 0 .54 which was statistically not Significant at 0.01 level of significance ($p=0.01$).

Results : The result showed that there was statistically significant effect of performance, Cognitive anxiety, and self-confidence and positive correlation between pre and post test performance, Cognitive anxiety, Somatic anxiety and self-confidence. There is no correlation between somatic anxiety of Shot-Put athletes.

Conclusions

From the view of the study and result we can conclude that....

- The training module brought change in anxiety level of the shot- put athlete performance.
- The somatic anxiety of players showed positive changes due to the training module.
- There was increase self-confidence due to the intervention of training.
- There was significance correlation between the performance, Cognitive anxiety and self confidence.
- The training module increases the performance of athlete.

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